

Research Article

Imaging Mentality: Focus on fMRI

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Abstract

Currently, most neuroscience efforts are focused on developing technologies based on the idea that our mental processes are based on synaptic connections between sets of neurons, exemplified by the Connectome Project. Technologies of physics have been adapted to study the brain, notably with fMRI (focused magnetic resonance imaging). The medical fMRI technique detects mainly the H in water (H₂O) or blood in the brain, as it is the relatively a much stronger signal than any H bound to tissue. The resultant "negative" image is generated by ignoring the signals of water and blood. Thus, we contemplate the "negative" image of the flesh of the whole brain. A major flaw in all the above-cited works is that they do not consider the neural extracellular matrix (nECM) as relevant to the brain's mentality. This in spite of published works describing the composition, structure and relevance of the nECM to neuron function. Thus, they are unable to suggest a credible mechanism for brain mentality.

We have proposed a tripartite mechanism of memory which involves the interactions of neurons with their surrounding extracellular matrix (nECM). The neurons encode incoming perceptions into the nECM by ejecting trace metal cations and neurotransmitters (NTs).

This generates a bio-chemical emotive memory code that is achievable by neural circuits employing available materials and processes. We have discussed how the limitations of the fMRI technique "blinds" the neurobiologists to the presence and role of the nECM around the neurons. A few experiments are suggested that would clarify the mechanism of neural mentality pointing to a nexus between chemodynamic and electrodynamic signaling.

We may not be able to penetrate the "event horizon" of mentality, but such experiments will help establish the limits of our understanding.

Keywords: fMRI / tripartite memory/ cognitive information/ chemodynamic/ consciousness

Introduction

"If I can't picture it, I can't understand it."

Albert Einstein

Mentality defies our much vaunted scientific enterprise. In contrast to physics which has tools to graphically and mathematically describe physical reality, we have no means of visualizing our psychic experience. Psychologists may analyze our mental states with words but provide no pictures of our mental processes which must be biochemical in nature, witness the many drugs that alter mood and memory.

The only psychic talent over which we seem to have some inkling is memory. Humans invented writing to help remember lists and events. In modern times, we developed a binary Information Theory and invented computers with dynamic memory functions that recall with algorithms embedded in "memory chips" [1-4]. But all this is superficial as far as our psychic memory ability is concerned.

We pose two questions which are really one:

What processes occur in our brains that instigate mental states?

How is caloric energy transcended into emotive thoughts and memories?

Currently, most neuroscience efforts are focused on developing technolo-

gies based on the idea that our mental processes are based on synaptic connections between sets of neurons, exemplified by the Connectome Project [5-8]. Indeed, the Connectome's effort main goal is to visualize the neural circuitry, to map the human brain network. It is inspired by the notion that visualizing the structural architecture of the neural circuitry will clarify its achievement of mentality. For the purposes of this discourse, we assign the same meaning to the terms "mentation", "cognition", "thought", all linked to subjective experiences of emotions and memory.

In that spirit, technologies of physics have been adapted to study the brain, notably with MRI (magnetic resonance imaging). This is an electro-magnetic effect, originally termed NMR (nuclear magnetic resonance), a technique employed by chemists to detect and characterize the electronic environment of hydrogen (H) bound to different sites on molecules [9,10]. For example, a particular H would exhibit a characteristic energy resonance (chemical shift) that might be perturbed by a neighboring H resulting in characteristic splitting of the signals (Figure 1). , which was developed on the basis of NMR (Nuclear Magnetic Resonance). The saying "NMR is the eyes of the chemist" aptly describes the crucial role of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy in modern chemistry. NMR allows chemists to "see" molecular structures and interactions at an atomic level, providing invaluable insights into chemical compounds and reactions.

Figure 1. NMR spectra of A. water (H₂O) B. methanol (CH₃OH) C ethanol (C₂H₅OH). glucose (C₆H₆ O₆) [9].

Key innovations in MRI include the use of magnetic field gradients for spatial encoding, development of pulse sequences for different types of tissue contrast, and the introduction of functional MRI (fMRI) for neural imaging. Medical use (MRI) was developed to non-invasively scan the H in whole bodies and brains of patients with various conditions.

It is really a type of "negative" image wherein the water (blood) is ignored leaving us to contemplate the "negative" image of the flesh of the whole brain (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Whole body MRI

For brain studies, neurobiologists adapted this to functional MRI (fMRI) where they asked the patient to look at images or engage in a mental activity while imaging the brain, termed fMRI. To be clear, the medical fMRI technique detects mainly the H in water (H₂O) or blood in the brain, as

Figure 3. MRI of man brain in various stages of memory loss (adapted from Liu et al. PLoS one (2012) 2, e31302).

A variant of the fMRI technology was developed by combining optogenetic modifications of neurons analyzed by "of MRI" with images processed by computational techniques. Thus, by genetically modifying some cells with fluorescent tags, "of MRI" has been used to detect cell synaptic activity across the whole brain. This permitted functions of discrete anatomic regions to be "parameterized" (i.e. visualized) [12]. For example, clinical neuroimaging results pointed to the front rather than the back of the cortex as relating to consciousness [13].

Another approach to whole brain imaging was developed that

Figure 4. Diffusion MRI imaging — called tractography — of the bundles of axons that neurons send throughout the brain's white matter, which lies interior to the cortex gray matter at the surface of the brain. The images reveal the communications circuitry extending throughout the white matter from the surrounding cortex. (An T. Vu, UCSF, and David Feinberg, UC Berkeley and Advanced MRI)

enabled 3D RNA imaging of the whole brain of mice by in situ hybridization after administration of an anti-obesity drug [14].

While all this technology is very impressive, something is still missing. Much was written about neural signaling but nothing about the transcendence of "signal" into "thought". None of the above-cited works discussed the mentality achieved by the brain or permitted one to "picture" a mental activity. The "elephant in room" (i.e. mentality) was not brought up, only neural signaling discussed.

Questions

- How is memory actuated in the brain?
- How do neural connections generate mental states?
- What is the neural code for emotive states?

Tripartite Mechanism [14, 20]

A major flaw in all the above-cited works is that they do not consider the neural extracellular matrix (nECM) as relevant to the brain's mentality. This in spite of numerous published works describing the relevance of the nECM to neuron functioning [15, 16]. As an exemplar of mentality, the tripartite mechanism of memory involves the interactions of neurons with their surrounding extracellular matrix (nECM). The neurons encode incoming perceptions into the nECM by ejecting trace metal cations and neurotransmitters (NTs). These locate within electron-rich "addresses" in the nECM to form metal-centered complexes i.e. **cognitive units of information** (*cuinfo*). Such a bio-chemical code for memory has many credible features [17-20]. Notably, it is achievable by neural circuits employing available materials and processes. as enumerated:

1. trace metals (see ref. [18-20]),
2. nECM synthesized by the neurons (15, 16 and many refs in Marx&Gilon)
3. Encodes emotive (affective) states with NTs, a biochemical code (n>100).

NT complexation confers emotive qualities to the memory.

As far as we know, nobody has ever designed a coding system with n~100, as compared to the binary (n=2) code (e.g. 0 1). Currently, we have no theoretical construct of a neural memory code. We do know that the nECM serves as the "library" while the metal cations and the NTs are the encoding "dopants", as chemographically presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Chemographic representations of the tripartite mechanism whereby neurons encode experience into the nECM with trace metal cations and neurotransmitter (NT) for later recall. The binding of NT to the metal-centered cognitive unit of information (*cuinfo*) entangles physiologic reactions with psychic experience.

To be clear, we may have identified the major components of the neural memory mechanism, but we have not cracked the neural memory code. Unlike the Information Theory with its binary (n=2) information (info) encoders (0 1), we don't have a clue how the neural system encodes cognitive information (cog-info) with a multitude of encoding elements (i.e. n>90) comprising >10 metal cations, with >80 NTs that engender emotions. It seems even beyond the vaunted capabilities of quantum comput-

ers with fractional states [17]. there is no rational code for emotive states. It seems that Life and Conscious Emotions may be inextricably linked phenomena.

Oversights of fMRI

The tripartite mechanism throws the limitation of the fMRI technique into sharp relief. That is, it points out that one cannot suggest a process for

brain mentality while ignoring a major structural component that affects the functionality of the neural circuits. As fMRI cannot "see" the nECM, it therefore ignores it, in spite of its descriptions in a number of reports [15, 16]. Exaggerated examples of such oversights are illustrated in Figure 6, where the matrix surroundings of fish, birds, plant and neuron are not considered as having functional relevance.

Figure 6. Images of birds, fish, plant and neuron are presented as if they function in the absence of a surrounding matrix.

Conclusion

Mentality, manifest as memory, is the big "bugaboo" of neurobiology.

Much ink has been expended to rationalize our mental talents. Theologians proffer "souls" as the engines of the mind. Psychologists expand in never-ending cascades of specialized words (pathology of various types, complexes, fixation on mother, father, brother, sister, etc). The premise of neurobiologists trying to comprehend the workings of the brain is that visualizing the synaptic connections between neurons will expose the mechanism driving mentality. We have discussed how the limitations of the fMRI technique blinds the neurobiologists to the presence and role of the nECM around the neurons. fMRI simply does not "see" the nECM and does not consider it in any functional schema.

Haiku to Facts

A mirage is not a truth.

A desire is not a fact.

The scientific method distinguishes truth and fact

From misconception and wishful thinking.

Experimental nECM

Two sets of objective experiments have pointed to the influence of nECM in the functioning of the neural net, as follows:

1. Impedance electrodes coated with NTs or tetrasaccharide analogues of the nECM were shown to be highly sensitive to trace metals, notably Zn^{+2} and Cu^{+2} [22-24]. These effects entangle chemodynamic processes with electrodynamic signaling.
2. Neurons were cultured on a multi-electrode array. Tissue-specific extracellular matrix (ECM) extracted from different sources was added. Depending on the particular ECM that was added, the formation of neural networks and communities in a neuron-glia co-culture was accelerated, there was increased network burst rate associated with robust synaptophysin expression. It was noted that the addition of ECM to neuronal cultures augmented the development of mature neural networks [25]. This group was further able to report on novel 3D culture prototypes with ECM to probe neural activity throughout

the 3D neural tissue [26]. Other groups have also reported on the important role of the nECM in brain function [15-20, 27].

Thus, fMRI overlooking the presence of nECM in brain tissue leads to mis-understanding how the brain functions. Visualizing neural synaptic contacts is important, but does not provide a complete concept. This is particularly acute for a phenomenon whose working we do not comprehend such as mentation manifest as memory and emotions.

We suggest some experiments to clarify the phenomenon of brain mentality, as follows:

1. Characterize nECM in different anatomical regions (variants: sulfation & charge distribution, describe the of amount tenascin and other proteins within the nECM.
2. Quantitate the distribution of metal elements in different a brain anatomic compartments (i.e. Zn, Cu, Mn, Fe, etc).
3. Stain for the distribution of diffent neurotransmitters (NTs) in different anatomic compartments.
4. Continue evaluating the effects of exogenous ECM added to neuron cultures on multi-electrodes [25-27].

Experiments with NTs coated on impedance electrodes were able to detect trace metal cations. Similarly, saccharide coating on electrodes could also be used to electrodynamically detect metal cations [22-24]. Such coated electrodes confirm the idea that neural memory could be encoded with metal-centered complexes within the nECM. They also suggest a nexus between chemodynamic and electrodynamic signaling.

We may not be able to penetrate the "event horizon" of mentality, but such experiments will help establish the limits of our understanding.

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(CG and GM): Our collaboration exemplifies the sage proverb: "*Iron sharpens iron, and one man sharpens the face of his neighbor*" to mean that in a good collaboration, one mind sharpens the abilities of the other. (Mishlei, Proverbs 27:17).

Conflict of Interest

GM is a founder of MX Biotech Ltd., with a commercial goal to develop biotechnology for wound healing and biomimetic sensors.

CG is emeritus professor of Hebrew University, but is active in developing and patenting peptide-based tools for surgery and pharmacology.

Notwithstanding, the ideas forwarded here are scientifically genuine and presented in good faith, without commercial clouding of the concepts expressed here.

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